

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DELAYED CORROSION CRACKING OF INFINITE PLATE WITH CIRCULAR APERTURE

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ABSTRACT

Delayed corrosion cracking of infinite thin isotropic elastic loaded metal plate with a circular aperture which is under the action of corrosive environment is theoretically investigated. Two cases of loading are considered: 1) circle aperture of the plate is loaded along the contour by uniform pressure, 2) circular aperture of the plate is loading free, however plate is exposed to uniform stress. Analytical formula for the time before corrosion cracking of plate depending on loading and data of plate and corrosive environment are performed in both considered cases. In order to illustrate the mentioned formulae, corresponding graphics were constructed.

Keywords: corrosion failure, corrosion potential, temperature, stress, metal – corrosive environment.

I. Introduction.

It is known that at simultaneous action of strain and corrosive environment on construction, the corrosion failure (cracking) occurs generally of metal units of this construction. Except of strain, temperature, concentration of active components of corrosive environment and corrosion potential [1, 2] have essential influence on corrosion process.

II. Objective.

During investigation of corrosion cracking process the main problem is in establishing dependence of time before corrosion cracking on strain, temperature, concentration of components of corrosive environment and corrosion potential. In [3] the formula allowing to determine time before corrosion cracking of structural element subject to investigation in corrosive environment under the action of certain mechanical forces or without them. This formula also allows to determine coordinates of points where the cracking begins.

$$\sigma_e = \frac{1-\lambda}{2} 3\sigma + \frac{1+\lambda}{2} \sigma_+, \quad (1)$$

where $\lambda = \sigma'_{lim}/\sigma''_{lim}$; $\sigma'_{lim}, \sigma''_{lim}$ are ultimate stresses at simple strain and simple contraction without the action of corrosive environment; $0 < \lambda \leq 1$; $\sigma = (\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})/3$ is average stress,

$$\sigma + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \left[(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + (\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + (\sigma_{33} - \sigma_{11})^2 + 6(\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{23}^2 + \sigma_{31}^2) \right]^{1/2}$$

is the stress intensity. There are also other formulae for σ_e [3,4].

Formula for time $t_x(x)$ derived by L.Kh.Talybly in paper [3], has the form

$$t_*(x) = Lt_0(\sigma_e(x), T(x), C(x), U(x)) - Rt_0(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \quad (2)$$

Here $\sigma_e = \sigma_e(x)$ is equivalent stress, $T = T(x)$ is stationary temperature field, $C = C(x)$ is stationary concentration, $U = U(x)$ is stationary corrosion potential. In order to define these values one should use the corresponding statements of problems. Function t_0 is regarded as universal function of system "metal - corrosive environment", and therefore it can be defined from exponents as a time before metal cracking at various constant values of each parameters σ_e, T, C, U . Statement and results of such experiments are given, e.g., in [1, 2]. Quantities L, R, a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 are universal material constants. They are also defined from simple experiments on delayed corrosion failure in which by turns one of the parameters change, even by the unknown law with respect to time and others remain constant. Note that constants a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 correspond to limiting values of parameters

σ_e, T, C, U at their behaviour in time during corrosion process. For example, constant a_1 can be defined from experiments on delayed corrosion failure at constant loading and fixed constant values $T = T_s = const, C = C_s = const, U = U_s = const$, since in this case during the corrosion time variation of stress occurs. For example, equation for defining a_1 will have the form

$$t_* = Lt_0(\sigma_0, T_s, C_s, U_s) - Rt_0(a_1, T_s, C_s, U_s)$$

where $\sigma_0 = const$ is rated stress of pattern from applied constant loading, i.e. stress calculated by initial sectional area. In this case quantity t_* is defined from experiment. Function t_0 is approximated subject to the type of given experimental curve of delayed corrosion failure obtained for parameters which remain constant or for approximate constant. Some formulae t_0 for are given in [3]. Here following [3], we cite one of the possible formulae for t_0 :

$$t_0 = t_0(\sigma_e, T, C, U) = \left[\frac{1}{t_{os}} + B_1 \left(\frac{\sigma_e}{\sigma_s} - 1 \right)^{\beta_1} + B_2 \left(\frac{T}{T_s} - 1 \right)^{\beta_2} + \beta_3 \left(\frac{C}{C_s} - 1 \right)^{\beta_3} + \beta_4 \left(\frac{U}{U_s} - 1 \right)^{\beta_4} \right]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

Here B_i, β_i ($i = \overline{1, 4}$) are material constants, $\sigma_s, T_s, C_s, U_s = const$ are stress, temperature, concentration and potential of reduction to dimensionless quantities. These quantities must be correspondent to lower values in range of changing of parameters σ_e, T, C, U , t_{os} – be time before cracking at $\sigma_e = \sigma_s, T = T_s, C = C_s, U = U_s$. Usually $\frac{1}{t_{os}} \rightarrow 0$. If corrosion process occurs under the strain σ_e at fixed values of T, C, U , then assuming that $T = T_s, C = C_s, U = U_s$, from (3) we obtain

$$t_0 = t_0(\sigma_e, T_s, C_s, U_s) = B_1^{-1} \left(\frac{\sigma_e}{\sigma_s} - 1 \right)^{-\beta_1} \equiv A \left(\frac{\sigma_e}{\sigma_s} - 1 \right)^{-\beta_1} \quad (4)$$

For $\beta_1 = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\sigma_e = \sigma_1$ where σ_1 is constant tension stress, formula (4) coincides with the well-known Rabotnov formula [5] which was checked by Zhukov's experiments [6] on corrosion cracking of brass in ammonium medium at constant deformation (with some approximation at constant stress). At that it was found that $\sigma_s = 46 MPa, A = 3,67 hour$. Experimental points and their approximative line constructed subject to formula (4) are represented in fig.1 (curve 1).

As it was noted in [3] stated above technique for defining constants contained in formula (2) is not unique one. Approximative form (3) of function t_0 is not unique too. Besides, as we can see formula (3) of L.Kh.Talybly [3] also holds in the case when corrosion process without action of strain.

IV. Result.

Now using aforecited formulae we will solve problem on corrosion failure of infinite thin isotropic elastic metal plate with circular aperture of radius a which is under the action of corrosive environment. Let us consider two cases of loading.

Case 1. Circular aperture of the plate is loaded along the contour by uniform pressure P_a . We will accept polar system of coordinates. Since plate is in elastic state, then radial and hoop nominal stresses are represented in the form [7]:

$$\sigma_r = -P_a \left(\frac{a}{T} \right)^2, \quad \sigma_\varphi = P_a \left(\frac{a}{T} \right)^2, \quad (5)$$

which satisfies the boundary conditions $\sigma_r|_{r=a} = -Pa, \sigma_r|_{r \rightarrow \infty} \rightarrow 0$. It is clear that at each point of plate pure shear state occurs. At that, average stress $\sigma = 0$, and stress intensity has the form

$$\sigma_+ = \left(\sigma_r^2 - \sigma_r \sigma_\varphi + \sigma_\varphi^2 \right)^{1/2}. \quad (6)$$

Subject to (5) from (6) we obtain $\sigma_+ = \sqrt{3}P_a \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^2$. By using formula (1) we find equivalent stress $\sigma_+ = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}(1 + \lambda)P_a \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^2$. Both in this case and in the next case of loading of plate we will assume that corrosion cracking process of plate occurs at constant temperature $T = T_s$, concentration $C = C_s$ and potential $U = U_s$. This allows to use formula (4) for function t_0 :

$$\frac{t_0}{A} = \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}(1 + \lambda) \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^2 \frac{P_a}{\sigma_s} - 1 \right]^{-\beta_1} \tag{7}$$

We will determine time before corrosion cracking by formula (2) which by using (7) and under the conditions $T = T_s$, $C = C_s$, $U = U_s$ turns to the form:

$$\frac{t_*(r)}{A} = L \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}(1 + \lambda) \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^2 \frac{P_a}{\sigma_s} - 1 \right]^{-\beta_1} - R \left(\frac{a_1}{\sigma_s} - 1 \right)^{-\beta_1} \tag{8}$$

Cracking of considered plate will begin at points $r = a$ where according to (8) quantity $t_*(r)/A$ at this point possesses the maximal value. Consequently, time before beginning corrosion failure of plate will be defined by the formula

$$\frac{t_*(a)}{A} = L \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}(1 + \lambda) \frac{P_a}{\sigma_s} - 1 \right]^{-\beta_1} - R \left(\frac{a_1}{\sigma_s} - 1 \right)^{-\beta_1} \tag{9}$$

In order to construct a graphic of dependence $\frac{P_a}{\sigma_s} \sim \frac{t_*}{A}$ we will use numerical data which are defined in [3] on the basis of experiments [6] on delayed corrosion failure of brass pattern in ammonium medium under the action of constant loading $A = 3,67 \text{ hour}$; $L = 0,567$; $R \left(\frac{a_1}{\sigma_s} - 1 \right)^{-\beta_1} = 0,256$; $\beta_1 = 0,5$. Graph of dependence $\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}(1 + \lambda) \frac{P_a}{\sigma_s} \sim \frac{t_*(a)}{A}$ constructed on the basis of equation (9) at given data is represented in fig.1 (curve 2).

Case 2. Circular aperture of plate is loading free. However, it is exposed to uniform tension at infinity by uniform pressure P_∞ . At that $\sigma_r = 0$ for $r = a$, $\sigma_r \rightarrow P_\infty$ at $r \rightarrow \infty$. Stress components σ_r and σ_φ are defined by formulae [7]

$$\sigma_r = P_\infty \left[1 - \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^2 \right], \quad \sigma_\varphi = P_\infty \left[1 + \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^2 \right] \tag{10}$$

At that average stress σ is equal to $\sigma = (\sigma_r + \sigma_\varphi)/3 = 2P_\infty/3$. On the basis of formula (6), stress intensity takes the form $\sigma_+ = P_\infty \left[1 + \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^4 \right]^{1/2}$. By using expressions for σ and σ_+ on the basis of formula

(1) we will calculate equivalent stress σ_e :

$$\sigma_e = P_\infty \left[1 - \lambda + 0,5(1 + \lambda) \left(1 + 3 \frac{a^4}{r^4} \right)^{1/2} \right].$$

Equivalent stress σ_e has the maximal value at $r = a$:

$$\sigma_{e\max} = \sigma_e \Big|_{r=a} = 2P_\infty = \sigma_\varphi \Big|_{r=a} = \sigma_{\varphi\max}.$$

Consequently, on application of relations (2) and (4) failure of plate in the considered case is defined by formula

$$\frac{t_*(a)}{A} = L \left(\frac{2P_\infty}{\sigma_s} - 1 \right)^{-\beta_1} - R \left(\frac{a_1}{\sigma_s} - 1 \right)^{-\beta_1} \tag{11}$$

If we will use numerical data mentioned above for brass in ammonium medium, then graphic of dependence $P_\infty / \sigma_s \sim t_*(a) / A$ constructed in accordance with formula (11), has the form of curve 3 in fig.1.

It follows from represented graphics 2 and 3 in fig.1 that at increasing values P_a and P_∞ time before failure of plate decreases. At the same time one can also conclude from these graphs that these are values of quantities P_a and P_∞ at which lower values rate of corrosion failure of plate significantly decreases.

Fig. 1.

Curves of delayed corrosion cracking: 1 - of brass pattern in ammonium medium under the action of constant tension stress σ_0 (points - are experimental data [6], firm line is approximation by formula (4) [5]; 2,3 - of infinite brass plates in ammonium medium with loaded uniform pressure P_a along the contour of circular aperture (2 - calculation by equation (9)) and with loading free circular aperture under the uniform tension at infinity by uniform pressure P_∞ (3 - calculation by equation (11)); $\sigma_s = 46MPa$, $A = 3,67$ hour.

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